

Removal of antibiotics through fixed bed adsorption: Comparison of different breakthrough curve models

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Abstract

Fixed bed adsorption serves as an effective method for eliminating organic micropollutants, including antibiotics, from water. To evaluate the performance of fixed bed adsorbers, researchers typically rely on the use of breakthrough curve models. Of particular significance is the accuracy of these models in predicting the time at which a specific breakthrough concentration occurs. In this study, we conducted a comparative analysis of four distinct breakthrough curve models. Within this set of models, the Thomas and Yan models are well-established, while the log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim models are more recent additions to the field. The log-Gompertz model is essentially empirical, whereas the Chu–Hashim model represents a modified version of the Thomas model. The Chu–Hashim model incorporates the concept of steric hindrance, accounting for the decline in the rate of adsorption as the adsorber approaches saturation. Our modeling study revolved around the adsorptive removal of antibiotics, specifically flumequine and tetracycline. The findings revealed that both the Thomas and Yan models provided poor correlations to the experimental breakthrough data. Furthermore, they consistently underestimated the time at which a specific breakthrough concentration was reached. The Thomas model performed the worst in this respect. In contrast, both the log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim models correlated well with the experimental breakthrough data, with the Chu–Hashim model consistently delivering superior correlations. Additionally, the breakthrough times predicted by these recently introduced models closely

aligned with the experimental times, showcasing their practical utility and superiority over the widely used Thomas and Yan models.

Keywords: Asymmetric breakthrough curve; Chu–Hashim model; log-Gompertz model; Thomas model; Yan model

1. Introduction

Despite being typically present in low concentrations, organic micropollutants, which include a diverse range of chemical categories such as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, industrial chemicals, and personal care products, have the ability to disrupt ecosystems. They can negatively impact the growth and reproductive capabilities of aquatic organisms and may even result in the decline of specific species. Furthermore, certain organic micropollutants have been found to pose detrimental effects on human health, ranging from acute toxicity to chronic health issues. The potential of these compounds to contribute to the development of antibiotic resistance and the emergence of new infectious diseases is also a growing concern.

Unlike conventional pollutants such as heavy metals and nutrients, organic micropollutants are generally not effectively eliminated by traditional wastewater treatment methods. To address this challenge, researchers are actively exploring advanced technologies, particularly adsorption processes, for the removal of organic micropollutants from wastewater. The primary adsorbents used in these adsorption processes are powdered activated carbon (PAC) and granular activated carbon (GAC) [1,2]. PAC consists of particles smaller than 100 μm and can be directly introduced into wastewater at various points within a municipal wastewater treatment plant. It is typically removed through processes like sedimentation or filtration [3]. On the other hand, GAC, with larger particle sizes exceeding 800 μm , is commonly used in a fixed bed configuration [1]. Nevertheless, there has been an attempt to use PAC in a fixed bed setup, in which the column was packed with PAC and sand particles [4].

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the application of a novel adsorbent called micro-grain activated carbon in pilot tests aimed at the removal of organic micropollutants [5–7]. This particular adsorbent is composed of particles within the size range of 100 to 800 μm , rendering it suitable for use in fluidized bed contactors. Furthermore, various other carbon-based adsorbent materials, including carbon nanotubes and graphene-based materials, have been synthesized and specifically assessed for their capacity to eliminate

antibiotics [8]. Despite these advances, PAC and GAC continue to be widely used in large-scale applications. This preference is partly attributed to their more predictable performance and the existence of well-established process design methodologies [9].

When the adsorbent is appropriately sized, the fixed bed configuration is typically preferred because it offers superior efficiency when compared to other process layouts. To assess the performance of these fixed bed adsorbers, breakthrough curves are commonly employed, and these curves can be easily measured in laboratory settings. The key information derived from experimental breakthrough data is the breakthrough time corresponding to a specific breakthrough concentration. By adjusting the operational parameters, a series of breakthrough curves can be generated, yielding a range of breakthrough times. This breakthrough data is most conveniently analyzed using mathematical models. Once a model is properly calibrated, it can be used to predict the breakthrough time corresponding to any desired breakthrough concentration. To ensure the success of the modeling approach, it is essential for the model to accurately represent the experimental breakthrough data acquired under various conditions.

The primary aim of this research was to evaluate and compare the predictive capabilities of two well-established models, namely Thomas and Yan, and two recently introduced models, log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim, by using experimental data pertaining to the adsorption of antibiotics in fixed bed adsorbers. As indicated in Table 1, the Thomas and Yan models have been extensively used to describe breakthrough curves for a variety of antibiotics, while the relatively new log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim models have received limited attention. The effectiveness of all four models in predicting breakthrough times corresponding to specific breakthrough concentrations was assessed through two distinct case studies. In the first case, the focus was on the adsorption of flumequine using a commercial GAC adsorbent, as reported by Sotelo et al. [20]. The second case examined the adsorption of tetracycline using a carbon-based material synthesized in a laboratory setting, as detailed by Zhang et al. [21]. Flumequine and tetracycline are antibiotics commonly used in the treatment of bacterial infections.

Table 1. Recent applications of the Thomas, Yan, and log-Gompertz models to antibiotic breakthrough data.

Ref.	Antibiotic/adsorbent	Model
Cheng et al. [10]	Tetracycline/manganese oxide	Thomas
Juela et al. [11]	Sulfamethoxazole/sugarcane bagasse	Yan; log-Gompertz
Antonelli et al. [12]	Ciprofloxacin/bentonite clay	Thomas; Yan
Almuntashiri et al. [13]	Metronidazole/activated carbon	Thomas
Aryee and Han [14]	Trimethoprim/peanut husk	Thomas; Yan
Spaolonzi et al. [15]	Cefazolin/bentonite clay	Thomas; Yan
Huang et al. [16]	Sulfamethoxazole, sulfapyridine/biochar	Thomas; Yan
Hou et al. [17]	Sulfamethoxazole/biochar	Thomas
de Oliveira et al. [18]	Tetracycline/activated carbon	Thomas; Yan; log-Gompertz
Antonelli et al. [19]	Sulfamethoxazole/clay	Thomas; Yan

2. Breakthrough curve models

2.1. The Thomas model

In Thomas's modeling approach [22], the equations for the flowing liquid phase within a fixed bed adsorber are represented by Eqs. (1)–(3), where v is the interstitial velocity, c is the contaminant concentration in the liquid phase at time t , x is the column axial coordinate, ρ_p is the adsorbent density, ε is the bed voidage, q is the average contaminant concentration in the adsorbent particles at time t , c_0 is the feed concentration, and L is the column length.

To describe the term $\partial q/\partial t$ in Eq. (1), which accounts for transport and kinetic resistances within the adsorbent particles, the Thomas modeling approach uses Eq. (4), where k_T is the rate coefficient and q_m and b are the Langmuir isotherm parameters. Eq. (4) is a reversible kinetic equation that follows a second-order forward reaction and a first-order reverse reaction. Based on the assumption of constant pattern, Walter [23] derived an analytical solution to the Thomas model, as presented in Eqs. (5)–(8), where q_0 represents the contaminant concentration in the adsorbed phase in equilibrium with the feed concentration c_0 .

$$v \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \rho_p \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$x=0, c = c_0 \quad (2)$$

$$x = L, \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = k_T \left[c(q_m - q) - \frac{q}{b} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[(1-R)(n - n\tau)]} \quad (5)$$

$$R = \frac{1}{1 + bc_0} \quad (6)$$

$$n = \frac{k_T \rho_p q_m L}{v} \left(\frac{1 - \varepsilon}{\varepsilon} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\tau = \frac{c_0}{\rho_p q_0} \left(\frac{vt}{L} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon} \right) \quad (8)$$

However, in water contaminant adsorption research, a simplified form of Eq. (5) is commonly used [24]. This simplified version is defined by Eq. (9), where m denotes the adsorbent mass and Q represents the volumetric flow rate. Typically, q_0 and k_T are treated as adjustable parameters that are fitted to experimental data. One advantage of Eq. (9) is that it does not require knowledge of the adsorbent density (ρ_p) and the bed voidage (ε). Additionally, it can be linearized.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k_T q_0 m / Q - k_T c_0 t)} \quad (9)$$

2.2. The Yan model

The breakthrough curve model introduced by Yan et al. [25] is represented by Eq. (10) and is based on a dose-response model used in pharmacology. This equation incorporates the empirical parameters α and β . In order to reduce the reliance on empirical parameters, Yan et al. [25] proposed Eq. (11) by substituting $1/\alpha$ with $c_0 Q / q_0 m$, which are variables derived from the Thomas model. Apiratikul and Chu [26] demonstrated that Eq. (11) can be transformed into Eq. (12), which corresponds to the well-known Hill equation frequently used in quantitative pharmacology.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + (t/\alpha)^\beta} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + (c_0 Q t / q_0 m)^\beta} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{(c_0 Q t / q_0 m)^\beta}{1 + (c_0 Q t / q_0 m)^\beta} \quad (12)$$

2.3. The log-Gompertz model

The Gompertz model, originally developed to explain human mortality trends, has recently been modified to take the form defined in Eq. (13), with t_0 set at 1 min and constants denoted as k_{G1} and k_{G2} . It should be noted that k_{G1} is a dimensionless parameter, whereas k_{G2} is expressed in units of min^{-1} . For the sake of simplicity, Eq. (13) is reformulated as Eq. (14) by omitting t_0 , which is equal to 1. This modified equation is referred to as the log-Gompertz model [27]. Table 1 shows that Juela et al. [11] and de Oliveira et al. [18] used this model to analyze breakthrough data related to the adsorption of sulfamethoxazole and tetracycline in fixed bed adsorbers, respectively.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \exp \left\{ -\exp \left[k_{G1} - t_0 k_{G2} \ln \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \exp \left[-\exp (k_{G1} - k_{G2} \ln t) \right] \quad (14)$$

2.4. The Chu–Hashim model

Jin et al. [28] modified Thomas's kinetic equation, Eq. (4), and transformed it into Eq. (15) in order to incorporate the effect of steric hindrance on the rate of adsorption. In Eq. (15), θ represents q/q_m and the coefficients B_1 and B_2 are functions of the relative binding site density [28]. Eq. (15) predicts a gradual reduction in the rate of adsorption caused by the obstruction of adsorbed molecules at high surface coverage. In essence, the modification involves multiplying the original rate coefficient k_T by the term $(1 - B_1\theta - B_2\theta^2)^2$. Consequently, as θ increases, the rate coefficient diminishes.

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = k_T \left[c(1 - \theta)(1 - B_1\theta - B_2\theta^2)^2 - \frac{\theta}{b} \right] \quad (15)$$

To simplify the consideration of steric hindrance, instead of employing a continuously decreasing rate coefficient as described in Eq. (15), a practical approach involves using two

separate rate coefficients. This concept draws inspiration from the steric hindrance model and involves transforming the Thomas (Walter) analytical solution [Eq. (9)] into Eq. (16), wherein two distinct rate coefficients, k_{CH1} and k_{CH2} , are introduced. In this new formulation, the effect of steric hindrance is neglected by k_{CH1} while being accounted for by k_{CH2} . Consequently, k_{CH1} is expected to be significantly larger than k_{CH2} . Eq. (16), known as the Chu–Hashim model, was briefly evaluated in a recent study [29].

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k_{CH1}q_0m/Q - k_{CH1}c_0t) + \exp(-k_{CH2}c_0t)} \quad (16)$$

2.5. Model fitting and evaluation

GraphPad Prism's nonlinear regression method was used to fit the aforementioned breakthrough curve models to two sets of previously published breakthrough data. The models were judged based on the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Akaike weight (AW), as defined below. The symbols and abbreviations used in Eqs. (17)–(21) and throughout the text are defined in the Nomenclature.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^z (E_i - M_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^z (E_i - E_m)^2} \quad (17)$$

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^z (E_i - M_i)^2 \quad (18)$$

$$AIC = z \ln \left(\frac{SSR}{z} \right) + \frac{2z(h+1)}{z-h-2} \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta_i = AIC_i - AIC_s \quad (20)$$

$$AW = 100 \frac{\exp(-0.5\Delta_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^w \exp(-0.5\Delta_j)} \quad (21)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Flumequine adsorption on GAC

Sotelo et al. [20] investigated the removal of flumequine from water using laboratory-scale fixed bed columns packed with Filtrasorb 400, a commercially available GAC adsorbent.

The authors examined various factors affecting the adsorption process, including the initial concentration, volumetric flow rate, and the quantity of adsorbent used. The resulting breakthrough curves were analyzed using the Thomas model. Fig. 1 illustrates a representative breakthrough curve, along with the corresponding fits of the four breakthrough curve models discussed in Section 2. The breakthrough run conditions are summarized in column 2 of Table 2.

The resulting Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu–Hashim model parameters, along with the R^2 and AW scores, are listed in Table 3. Panel A of Fig. 1 reveals the inadequacy of the Thomas model correlation, as indicated by an R^2 value of 0.923. This model failed to accurately capture the overall shape of the breakthrough curve. The predicted curve from the Thomas model was highly symmetric, contradicting the asymmetric shape of the experimental profile. The source of this asymmetry was attributed to the gradual approach to saturation during the final breakthrough phase, a phenomenon commonly referred to as “tailing.”

Fig. 1. Comparison of Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu–Hashim model correlations of experimental breakthrough data for flumequine on GAC [20].

Table 2. Experimental conditions for flumequine [20] and tetracycline [21] adsorption in fixed bed columns.

Parameter	Contaminant	
	Flumequine	Tetracycline
Adsorbent	Activated carbon	Hierarchical porous carbon
Adsorbent size (mm)	0.5–0.59	–
Feed concentration (mg cm ⁻³)	0.001	0.05
Column diameter (cm)	0.6	0.46
Packed bed length (cm)	6	3.5
Adsorbent mass (g)	0.6	0.05
Flow rate (cm ³ min ⁻¹)	1	1
Superficial velocity (cm min ⁻¹)	3.5	6
Empty bed contact time (min)	1.7	0.6

Table 3. Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu–Hashim model parameters obtained from fitting experimental breakthrough data for flumequine on GAC [20] and the resulting R^2 and AW scores.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Thomas	(9)	k_T	0.15 (0.02)	R^2	0.923
		q_0	59.94 (1.34)	AW	0
Yan	(12)	β	4.93 (0.43)	R^2	0.958
		q_0	58.8 (1.05)	AW	0
Log-Gompertz	(14)	k_{G1}	33.66 (1.80)	R^2	0.983
		k_{G2}	3.26 (0.17)	AW	0
Chu–Hashim	(16)	k_{CH1}	0.37 (0.02)	R^2	0.997
		k_{CH2}	0.02 (0.001)	AW	100
		q_0	50.96 (0.35)		

^a k_T , k_{CH1} , and k_{CH2} are in cm³ mg⁻¹ min⁻¹; q_0 is in mg g⁻¹; β and k_{G1} are dimensionless; k_{G2} is in min⁻¹; AW is in %.

A comparison between panels A and B of Fig. 1 demonstrates that the Yan model slightly outperformed the Thomas model in correlating the flumequine data, resulting in an R^2 value of 0.958 (Table 3). However, similar to the Thomas model, the Yan model tended to overestimate the effluent concentration during both the initial and final breakthrough phases. Shifting our attention to panel C, it is conspicuously clear that the correlation offered by the log-Gompertz model marked a substantial improvement over the fits obtained with the Thomas and Yan models, as signified by its R^2 score of 0.983. As we transition to panel D, it becomes abundantly clear that the Chu–Hashim model delivered an exceptional representation of the

experimental data ($R^2 = 0.997$). The results of the Akaike test (Table 3) provided full support for the Chu–Hashim model, with an AW of 100%. Thus, the use of three fitting parameters in the Chu–Hashim model to accurately describe the flumequine breakthrough data was clearly well justified.

By considering steric hindrance, the Chu–Hashim model effectively replicated the asymmetric shape of the experimental breakthrough curve. A glance at Table 3 reveals that the magnitude of k_{CH1} exceeded that of k_{CH2} by approximately 18 times. In essence, in the Chu–Hashim model the larger k_{CH1} was used to represent the rapid increase in effluent concentration during the initial breakthrough phase, while the notably smaller k_{CH2} was employed to describe the gradual tailing effect observed in the final breakthrough phase.

Fig. 2. Comparison of observed and predicted breakthrough times corresponding to a flumequine breakthrough concentration of $c/c_0 = 0.05$.

When evaluating breakthrough curve models, it is essential to consider their ability to accurately describe general data trends as well as their precision in estimating the breakthrough times corresponding to specific breakthrough concentrations. In the flumequine adsorption experiment conducted by Sotelo et al. [19], they reported a time of 366.3 h (21,978 min) when the breakthrough concentration of $c/c_0 = 0.05$ was achieved. Fig. 2 compares the experimental time to the breakthrough times predicted by the four models. Notably, the predictions of the Thomas and Yan models were approximately 26% and 12% shorter than the actual time,

respectively. Therefore, these models would lead to the premature termination of the fixed bed operation. In contrast, the log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim models provided accurate predictions of the experimental time, underscoring the practical utility of these recently proposed models.

3.2. Tetracycline adsorption on hierarchical porous carbon

In their study, Zhang et al. [21] delved into the fixed bed adsorption of tetracycline using a carbon-based material they synthesized in their own laboratory. This particular carbon adsorbent, known as hierarchical porous carbon, possessed a unique blend of micro and meso bimodal pores, and it demonstrated remarkable efficiency when compared to a commercial activated carbon adsorbent. The research encompassed the collection of several breakthrough curves under varying operational conditions, and these curves were later subjected to fitting with the Thomas model.

Fig. 3 displays a breakthrough curve taken from the work of Zhang et al. [21], and column 3 of Table 2 offers an overview of the experimental parameters. Much like the flumequine case discussed in Section 3.1, the fixed bed adsorption of tetracycline generated a breakthrough curve characterized by profound tailing. As shown in Fig. 3, this breakthrough curve exhibited a rapid ascent in the initial breakthrough phase, followed by a broadening phase as the fixed bed approached saturation.

Panels A and B of Fig. 3 showcase notable disparities between the correlations generated by the Thomas and Yan models and the experimental data. Both models tended to overestimate the effluent concentration during the initial and final breakthrough segments. Panel C, on the other hand, illustrates that the log-Gompertz model performed considerably better than the Thomas and Yan models. In Panel D, it becomes evident that the Chu–Hashim model provided a highly accurate representation of the experimental data, demonstrating its significant superiority over the other three models. The parameter estimates obtained from these model fits and the resulting statistical metrics are documented in Table 4. Both the R^2 and AW scores supported the visual comparisons made earlier. Moreover, the Akaike test decisively favored the Chu–Hashim model while rejecting the other three models completely. Table 4 further reveals that the fitted value of k_{CH1} was 15 times larger than that of k_{CH2} . This observation aligned with the result observed in the flumequine case, further substantiating the consistency of the Chu–Hashim model.

Fig. 3. Comparison of Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu-Hashim model correlations of experimental breakthrough data for tetracycline on hierarchical porous carbon [21].

Table 4. Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu-Hashim model parameters obtained from fitting experimental breakthrough data for tetracycline on hierarchical porous carbon [21] and the resulting R^2 and AW scores.^a

Model	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value
Thomas	(9)	k_T	0.22 (0.02)	R^2	0.931
		q_0	654.3 (8.6)	AW	0
Yan	(12)	β	6.52 (0.52)	R^2	0.952
		q_0	652.6 (7.4)	AW	0
Log-Gompertz	(14)	k_{G1}	29.37 (1.57)	R^2	0.976
		k_{G2}	4.6 (0.25)	AW	0
Chu-Hashim	(16)	k_{CH1}	0.45 (0.02)	R^2	0.992
		k_{CH2}	0.03 (0.001)	AW	100
		q_0	605.9 (2.6)		

^a k_T , k_{CH1} , and k_{CH2} are in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$; q_0 is in mg g^{-1} ; β and k_{G1} are dimensionless; k_{G2} is in min^{-1} ; AW is in %.

Accurately predicting the breakthrough time corresponding to a specific breakthrough concentration is of paramount importance, as emphasized previously. In the work of Zhang et al. [21], they recorded a time of 522.8 min, at which the breakthrough concentration of $c/c_0 = 0.1$ was reached. Fig. 4 provides a side-by-side comparison of the ~~the~~ observed breakthrough time with the predicted values generated by the four models. The Thomas and Yan models underestimated the experimental time by approximately 13% and 11%, respectively, resulting in a conservative appraisal of the adsorption capacity of the fixed bed column. Conversely, the log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim model breakthrough times matched well with the experimental time, with the Chu–Hashim model yielding a more precise prediction. In summary, the Chu–Hashim model showcased significant superiority over the widely used Thomas and Yan models, while also exhibiting a moderate advantage over the recently introduced log-Gompertz model.

Fig. 4. Comparison of observed and predicted breakthrough times corresponding to a tetracycline breakthrough concentration of $c/c_0 = 0.1$.

3.3. Taking a closer look at the Chu–Hashim model

The Chu–Hashim model has demonstrated its versatility in accurately capturing the asymmetric or tailing breakthrough data shown in Figs. 1 and 3. In contrast, the Thomas and Yan models encountered difficulties when attempting to accurately depict these highly skewed breakthrough patterns, and the log-Gompertz model exhibited less robust performance

compared to the Chu–Hashim model. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that previous research has highlighted the capability of the Thomas, Yan, and log-Gompertz models to accurately fit specific types of breakthrough data.

To explore whether the Chu–Hashim model can match the performance of these three models under similar circumstances, we conducted an investigation. This inquiry involved fitting the Chu–Hashim model to breakthrough curves generated by the other three models. The results of this investigation are presented in Fig. 5, which illustrates the fits of the Chu–Hashim models to the continuous lines displayed in panels A, B, and C of Fig. 3, generated by the three models. To enhance clarity, these model-generated profiles are presented as symbols in Fig. 5. It is apparent from the visual representation in Fig. 5 and the corresponding R^2 scores provided in Table 5 that the Chu–Hashim model effectively captured the profiles generated by the three models. These findings suggest that the Chu–Hashim model is well-suited to fitting experimental datasets that the Thomas, Yan, and log-Gompertz models can also accurately represent.

Fig. 5. Fitting the Chu–Hashim model to breakthrough profiles generated by the Thomas, Yan, and log-Gompertz models.

Table 5. Chu–Hashim model parameters obtained from fitting breakthrough profiles generated by the Thomas, Yan, and log-Gompertz models and the resulting R^2 scores.

Model	k_{CH1} ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	k_{CH2} ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	q_0 (mg g^{-1})	R^2
Thomas	0.22	0.22	654.2	1.0000
Yan	0.232	0.062	644.2	0.9997
Log-Gompertz	0.274	0.049	633.6	0.9985

An intriguing observation pertains to the estimated values of the Chu–Hashim rate coefficients, k_{CH1} and k_{CH2} . As presented in Table 5, when the Chu–Hashim model was fitted to the breakthrough profile generated by the Thomas model, it yielded an identical estimate for both k_{CH1} and k_{CH2} , which was $0.22 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This parameter estimate coincided with the value of the Thomas rate coefficient, k_T , listed in Table 4, which had been used in generating the Thomas breakthrough profile seen in panel A of Fig. 5. Consequently, we can infer that the Chu–Hashim model is capable of emulating the behavior of the Thomas model by assigning the same numerical value to both k_{CH1} and k_{CH2} . When k_{CH1} is equivalent to k_{CH2} , the breakthrough profiles produced by the Chu–Hashim model will be perfectly symmetric, aligning with the characteristics of the Thomas model, which is specifically designed for generating such symmetric breakthrough profiles.

4. Conclusions

In this research, a comparative analysis was carried out to assess the performance of the Thomas, Yan, log-Gompertz, and Chu–Hashim models in representing the experimental breakthrough data related to antibiotic adsorption on carbon adsorbents. Two case studies were undertaken, focusing on the breakthrough behavior of flumequine when adsorbed on GAC and tetracycline on hierarchical porous carbon. The findings revealed that the widely used Thomas model struggled to accurately describe the asymmetric nature of the experimental breakthrough curves. While the Yan model showed improvement over the Thomas model, it still displayed notable deviations. Both models fell short in their ability to accurately estimate the breakthrough times corresponding to specific breakthrough concentrations.

In contrast, the recently introduced log-Gompertz and Chu–Hashim models correlated well with the experimental breakthrough data, with the Chu–Hashim model outperforming the log-Gompertz model. The Chu–Hashim model effectively captured the asymmetric characteristics of the breakthrough data and its predictions for breakthrough times closely aligned with the experimental observations. The Chu–Hashim model’s superiority can be attributed to its incorporation of steric hindrance effects and the use of two distinct rate coefficients.

From a process design standpoint, the Chu–Hashim model proves to be more valuable than the empirical log-Gompertz model, as the former incorporates crucial fixed bed variables like flow rate and bed length. In summary, this study underscored the significance of choosing

the right breakthrough curve model for accurately depicting experimental breakthrough data and making precise predictions about breakthrough times. Furthermore, it highlighted the potential of the Chu–Hashim model as a reliable tool for designing and optimizing fixed bed adsorbers, particularly for the efficient removal of antibiotics from water.

Nomenclature

b	Langmuir equilibrium constant [$\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1}$]
c	Liquid phase concentration of sorbate [mg cm^{-3}]
c_0	Sorbate concentration in feed [mg cm^{-3}]
E	Experimental value of c/c_0 [–]
E_m	Mean of experimental c/c_0 [–]
h	Number of fitting parameters [–]
k_{G1}	Log-Gompertz parameter [–]
k_{G2}	Log-Gompertz parameter [min^{-1}]
k_T	Thomas rate coefficient [$\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$]
k_{CH1}	Chu–Hashim rate coefficient [$\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$]
k_{CH2}	Chu–Hashim rate coefficient [$\text{cm}^3 \text{mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$]
L	Length of packed bed [cm]
m	Mass of adsorbent [g]
M	Calculated value of c/c_0 [–]
n	Parameter defined by Eq. (7) [–]
q	Average sorbate concentration in adsorbed phase [mg g^{-1}]
q_0	Sorbate concentration in equilibrium with c_0 [mg g^{-1}]
q_m	Saturation concentration in Langmuir model [mg g^{-1}]
Q	Feed flow rate [$\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$]

R	Parameter defined by Eq. (6) [-]
R^2	Coefficient of determination [-]
t	Time [min]
t_0	Equivalent to 1 min
v	Interstitial liquid velocity [cm min ⁻¹]
w	Number of competing models [-]
x	Distance measured from column inlet [cm]
z	Number of data points [-]

Greek letters

α	Yan parameter [min ⁻¹]
β	Yan parameter [-]
ε	Void fraction of packed bed [-]
θ	Dimensionless adsorbed phase concentration (q/q_m) [-]
ρ_p	Density of adsorbent [g cm ⁻³]
τ	Parameter defined by Eq. (8) [-]
Δ_i	AIC value calculated from Eq. (20) [-]

Abbreviations

AIC	Corrected Akaike Information Criterion [-]
AIC _{<i>i</i>}	AIC value for the <i>i</i> -th model [-]
AIC _{<i>s</i>}	AIC value for the model with the lowest score [-]
AW	Akaike weight [%]
GAC	Granular activated carbon
PAC	Powdered activated carbon
SSR	Sum of squared residuals [-]

Author contributions

All authors contributed equally.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data statement

All data used in this manuscript are publicly available or can be obtained by contacting the corresponding author.

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